

E1A binding protein p300 / histone acetyltransferase p300 (EP300) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

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Abstract

Histone acetyltransferase p300 (p300 HAT) or adenovirus early region 1A(E1A)-associated protein p300 (EP300) gene encodes the adenovirus E1A-associated cellular p300 transcriptional co-activator protein. It functions as histone acetyltransferase that regulates transcription of genes via chromatin remodeling by allowing histone proteins to wrap DNA less tightly. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 EP300 related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for EP300-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Support vector ranking, Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) and Sobol indices, WNT3A

[☆]Time behavioural study of 3-odr EP300 comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

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1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of ${}^{71}C_3$ (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search done by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order EP300 related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination, then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. E1A binding protein p300 / histone acetyltransferase p300 (EP300)

The growth-controlling functions of the adenovirus E1A oncoprotein depend on its ability to interact with a set of cellular proteins. Among these are the retinoblastoma protein, p107, p130, and p300. Eckner et al. [4] isolated a cDNA encoding full-length human p300 and mapped the chromosomal location of the gene on the long (q) arm of the human chromosome 22 at position 13.2. They show that p300 contains three cysteine- and histidine-rich regions of which the most carboxy-terminal region interacts specifically with E1A. In its center, it contains a bromodomain which is a hallmark of certain transcriptional coactivators.

Bromodomain was identified as a novel structural motif when Tamkun et al. [5] showed that the *brhma* (BRM) gene is required for the activation of multiple homeotic genes in *Drosophila*. BRM encodes a 1638 residue protein that is similar to SNF2SWI2, a protein involved in transcriptional activation in yeast, suggesting possible models for the role of BRM in the transcriptional activation of homeotic genes. In addition, both BRM and SNF2 contain a 77 amino acid motif that is found in other *Drosophila*, yeast, and human regulatory proteins and may be characteristic of a new family of regulatory proteins.

Ogryzko et al. [6] demonstrate that p300/CBP is not only a transcriptional adaptor but also a histone acetyltransferase. Is a transcriptional adaptor that integrates signals from many sequence-specific activators via direct interactions. The cellular p300/CBP associated factor (PCAF) possesses intrinsic histone acetyltransferase activity, that targets p300/CBP to modulate transcription and/or cell cycle progression. p300/CNP acetylates all four core histones in nucleosomes and Various cellular and viral factors.

Histone acetylation helps in chromatin remodelling and gene activation. Nearly all known histone-acetyltransferase (HAT)-associated transcriptional co-activators contain bromodomains (approximately 110-amino-acid modules found in many chromatin-associated proteins). Dhalluin et al. [7] reported the solution structure of the bromodomain of the HAT co-activator P/CAF (p300/CBP-associated factor) which revealed an unusual left-handed up-and-down four-helix bundle. The nature of the recognition of acetyl-lysine by the P/CAF bromodomain is similar to that of acetyl-CoA by histone acetyltransferase. Thus, the bromodomain is functionally linked to the HAT activity of

co-activators in the regulation of gene transcription.

Owen et al. [8] report the crystal structure at 1.9 Å resolution of the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* GCN5P bromodomain complexed with a peptide corresponding to residues 1529 of histone H4 acetylated at the ζ -N of lysine 16. They show that this bromodomain preferentially binds to peptides containing an N-acetyl lysine residue. Only residues 1619 of the acetylated peptide interact with the bromodomain. Zeng and Zhou [9] summarize the bromodomains as an acetyl-lysine binding domain. The 61 bromodomains (BRDs) in the human genome cluster into eight families based on structure/sequence similarity. Filippakopoulos et al. [10] present 29 high-resolution crystal structures, covering all BRD families.

I present 3rd order combinations of EP300 with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different time points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [11]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [11].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations

between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use `source("mainScript-1-1.R")` with arguments for Dynamic data • `source("SVMRank-Results-D.R")`, to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use `source("Combine-Time-files.R")`, if computing indices separately via previous file, • `source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R")` to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use `source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R")` to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use `source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R")` to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using rnorm is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 EP300-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [12]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [13] and martinez implementation in Martinez [14] and Baudin et al. [15]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested EP300-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving EP300 were obtained from a full set of ${}^7C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria

for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of TCF-EP300-X combinations

Sun et al. [16] report that the transcriptional coactivator p300 interacts with β -catenin in vitro and in vivo and is critical for β -catenin-mediated neoplastic transformation. It was found to activate β -catenin/TCF transcription, and their biochemical association requires the CH1 domain of p300 and a region of β -catenin that includes its NH₂-terminal transactivation domain and the first two armadillo repeats. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of TCF family along with EP300, to be prominent at 3rd order level - AES-EP300-TCF7, AXIN1-EP300-TCF7, DVL1-EP300-TCF7, AES-EP300-TCF7L1, DVL1-EP300-TCF7L1, EP300-GSK3B-TCF7, EP300-LRP6-TCF7, EP300-FOXN1-TCF7L1, EP300-FZD2-TCF7L1 and EP300-PORCN-TCF7L1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of LEF1-EP300-X combinations

To test whether downstream components of the WNT/ β -catenin signal transduction pathway contribute to the differential regulation of Wnt target genes, Hecht and Stemmler [17] asked whether LEF1 and TCF4E were equally capable of supporting activation of WNT-regulated promoters by β -catenin and p300. At the Siamois promoter and in conjunction with LEF1, recruitment and activation of p300 by β -catenin appears to be sufficient. Also, their preliminary results indicated that TCF1E, but not TCF1B, which resembles LEF1, could cooperate with β -catenin and p300 to activate the CDX1 promoter. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for LEF1 along with EP300, to be prominent at 3rd order level - EP300-FZD2-LEF1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of CCND-EP300-X combinations

Hecht et al. [18] show that β -catenin and p300 synergize to stimulate a synthetic reporter gene construct, whereas activation of the CCND1 promoter by β -catenin is refractory to p300 stimulation. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of CCND family along with EP300, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FZD5-CCND2-EP300, FZD5-CCND1-EP300 and CCND1-CTBP1-EP300. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
DVL1-EP300-LRP5	45	28131	44550	28209	50928	AES-EP300-FRZB	107	47237	52432	18109	22006
DVL1-EP300-FRZB	116	18151	11685	9254	40545	AXINI-EP300-GSK3B	163	24228	14803	32053	17651
DVL1-EP300-GSK3B	207	32638	7688	33872	35334	DVL1-EP300-WNT2B	247	6893	42213	52392	47037
AES-EP300-TCF7	257	52340	43783	40882	1516	AES-EP300-FZD1	258	49278	55037	15347	47022
AES-EP300-SENP2	266	39979	55044	31248	12673	DVL1-EP300-WNT4	272	18110	37869	41167	44769
DVL1-EP300-FBXW11	404	20946	9783	53163	54751	DVL1-EP300-FZD1	420	47837	24856	16322	41749
AXINI-EP300-TCF7	421	7016	43416	54620	14023	EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	445	18545	22047	46724	18178
EP300-FBXW11-LRP6	502	27632	22035	22910	27044	EP300-LRP6-WNT2	638	44313	22577	3663	7256
EP300-GSK3B-RHOU	762	29861	9716	10624	2207	DVL1-EP300-SFRP4	803	36937	10257	53811	47697
AES-EP300-FBXW2	878	39324	31038	27397	3825	EP300-WNT1-WNT2	884	39083	11026	13187	5410
EP300-WNT1-WNT2B	940	30973	2609	12191	47783	EP300-GSK3B-TCF7	954	29218	27018	16078	23635
AXINI-DVL1-EP300	1031	6065	16319	47978	31309	AXINI-EP300-LRP5	1069	2036	46947	24321	4379
DKK1-EP300-FRZB	1088	10676	53202	44534	37008	EP300-GSK3B-SENP2	1093	42030	6696	7981	765
FZD5-CCND2-EP300	1109	33708	3119	30209	55972	EP300-RHOU-WNT2	1132	42400	48712	18390	28303
DVL1-EP300-TCF7	1158	46231	45665	56151	39460	AES-EP300-WNT5A	1232	50236	54302	23216	39305
EP300-FZD2-FZD7	1306	49961	52239	51266	19772	AXINI-EP300-RHOU	1312	1646	32903	47413	5408
EP300-FOXNI-TLE2	1334	6564	2241	419	8940	EP300-LRP6-TCF7	1342	30447	49509	44129	4032
EP300-WNT1-WNT3A	1360	30527	695	53063	7375	EP300-FZD2-SFRP4	1428	43571	54834	3371	29414
EP300-LRP6-RHOU	1441	36401	11469	47312	1505	DVL1-EP300-SLC9A3R1	1490	18769	9009	57150	34851
AES-EP300-FOSL1	1521	46072	48935	20712	49058	EP300-FGF4-FRAT1	1588	28152	39282	54116	41791
EP300-FOXNI-SFRP4	1612	6840	5991	389	280	EP300-FOXNI-KREMEN1	1620	7884	6802	739	13419
AES-EP300-TCF7L1	1631	44460	34641	28386	39724	EP300-FZD2-SENP2	1639	43293	36216	3329	8258
EP300-FGF4-FOSL1	1656	55025	38932	40354	51107	EP300-WNT1-WNT5A	1667	20162	16144	44114	26527
AES-EP300-TLE2	1736	45932	19846	34789	55409	EP300-GSK3B-SFRP4	1785	42024	20409	8178	12158
EP300-FOXNI-FRAT1	1814	1637	5045	2015	815	AXINI-EP300-SLC9A3R1	2064	7574	22759	53828	11686
EP300-GSK3B-WNT2B	2076	31297	1204	24013	16338	EP300-FGF4-WNT2	2093	38634	33059	42983	46200
AES-EP300-PITX2	2125	50901	43504	52709	17083	AXINI-EP300-FBXW4	2130	13751	7349	18366	36793
EP300-LRP6-SLC9A3R1	2241	54665	6734	14185	31200	EP300-GSK3B-WNT2	2254	34471	22817	3013	1572
EP300-GSK3A-SENP2	2275	42378	2094	22319	42143	DVL1-EP300-FBXW4	2314	4738	8056	35532	41452
EP300-FZD2-WNT2B	2320	24458	22441	44903	18140	EP300-FBXW11-WNT2	2352	32380	5400	26107	31089
EP300-GSK3A-WNT2	2458	45111	24489	42270	47520	AES-EP300-NLK	2549	52374	48380	27425	55437
AXINI-EP300-FRZB	2553	866	20410	2676	6170	EP300-PORCN-SENP2	2667	50915	5651	10035	52083
EP300-JUN-TLE2	2679	44828	31	25970	46852	EP300-FZD2-PPP2CA	2702	12448	13262	50046	20911
AES-EP300-FZD8	2713	38543	49818	22196	49165	EP300-FOXNI-FZD7	2714	25117	4781	3184	35097
EP300-GSK3B-SLC9A3R1	2733	48653	10966	10820	22885	EP300-PYG01-WNT2	2948	43158	15314	8724	20816
DVL1-EP300-FZD8	2951	29540	12120	18903	44386	DVL1-EP300-WNT5A	2981	45215	32109	50904	36947
EP300-FZD2-LRP5	3002	41575	22148	54563	13500	EP300-PORCN-WNT4	3047	52212	12666	11882	56673
EP300-FOXNI-PPP2R1A	3054	31254	9485	1045	4738	AXINI-EP300-SENP2	3106	10788	31481	23191	4091
EP300-FOXNI-FZD1	3113	1863	8770	1719	923	EP300-FOXNI-TCF7L1	3126	3782	3353	1217	4819
EP300-FZD2-WNT2	3139	39887	31858	26340	25585	EP300-JUN-WIFI	3213	26743	1259	1082	53260
AES-EP300-PPP2CA	3218	22740	43678	26060	41565	EP300-PORCN-SFRP1	3229	50142	13492	14922	54985
EP300-LRP6-FBXW4	3274	44837	28655	8993	14599	DKK1-EP300-LRP5	3312	11909	56702	45179	37104
EP300-SLC9A3R1-WNT2	3350	46806	34723	47893	8400	CCND1-CTBP1-EP300	3358	42042	42344	35857	48984
CTBP2-CTNBN1-EP300	3365	40136	27775	17397	7468	DVL1-EP300-KREMEN1	3366	29392	28100	54892	20990
EP300-PORCN-SFRP4	3399	53557	14432	13953	55277	DIXDC1-EP300-FBXW11	3401	6056	10476	24069	55750
EP300-FOXNI-FZD6	3411	4860	17749	501	25541	EP300-FRZB-FZD1	3480	44015	31205	1022	5684
EP300-FOXNI-LRP5	3486	2188	7346	15917	9396	AXINI-EP300-FZD1	3503	369	27768	3828	12795
EP300-PORCN-PPP2R1A	3588	55435	38638	36180	44771	EP300-FZD2-WNT4	3653	44086	18558	21712	24613
AXINI-EP300-WNT3A	3721	4489	13963	10072	11451	EP300-FZD2-TCF7L1	3731	10207	47941	32679	8909
AES-EP300-WNT2	3733	42752	47227	32967	26785	EP300-FZD2-PITX2	3771	12315	30396	16799	22718
DVL1-EP300-TCF7L1	3789	46595	17797	39924	51184	AES-EP300-KREMEN1	3796	45394	51834	52960	6499
EP300-FZD2-LEF1	3817	40487	19516	56270	7480	EP300-PORCN-WNT2B	3826	37202	48507	42391	54306
AXINI-EP300-LRP6	3878	5642	33651	11423	13761	DVL1-EP300-PITX2	3886	37126	11319	53194	36735
DKK1-EP300-SENP2	3891	20732	50914	37657	44749	EP300-GSK3A-NLK	3902	24187	13268	22163	37611
EP300-FBXW11-SENP2	3933	42083	2536	20991	19946	EP300-FOXNI-WNT2B	3966	8828	3051	1383	6560
EP300-FBXW11-FBXW4	4014	31495	811	16846	39181	EP300-FGF4-PPP2R1A	4059	54172	38740	54434	30530
FZD5-CCND1-EP300	4060	18083	4714	3951	48122	EP300-JUN-PPP2R1A	4089	45635	48485	28347	10942
EP300-FOXNI-RHOU	4098	4360	4723	4476	13723	EP300-FOXNI-WNT4	4156	11103	5561	886	8761
EP300-GSK3B-LRP5	4172	45460	31410	26873	1387	AXINI-EP300-WNT5A	4180	9970	29920	45061	25015
EP300-NKD1-WNT2	4238	5464	3982	38439	1323	AXINI-EP300-WNT4	4260	2683	36665	20580	7537
EP300-GSK3B-FBXW4	4291	44257	21194	7041	8080	AXINI-EP300-PITX2	4304	11293	12887	53659	13073
EP300-FOXNI-GSK3B	4325	2497	2297	15564	19880	EP300-PORCN-TCF7L1	4329	18128	11086	13559	52464
EP300-LRP6-SFRP4	4353	54017	12211	6672	17900	EP300-GSK3A-WNT2B	4370	31237	5657	53835	53021

Table 1: Rankings of EP300-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - RBF

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_2	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_2	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
DVLI-EP300-LRP5	52736	14122	3935	57133	11155	AES-EP300-FRZB	40882	51536	7119	33764	20536
DVLI-EP300-FRZB	50198	6937	30267	52396	2625	AXINI-EP300-GSK3B	35345	3731	2610	56872	11778
DVLI-EP300-GSK3B	53115	9324	29348	56804	16941	DVLI-EP300-WNT2B	53233	2104	15799	56735	2280
AES-EP300-TCF7	39855	49176	5264	28073	35221	AES-EP300-FZD1	38410	50414	31342	5312	36922
AES-EP300-SEN2	36742	43851	9360	56088	25857	DVLI-EP300-WNT4	44214	8987	34040	43683	919
DVLI-EP300-FBXW11	52680	9754	26824	56227	7252	DVLI-EP300-FZD1	40171	42833	3293	53576	7127
AXINI-EP300-TCF7	23920	5040	28002	41498	26154	EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	4639	142	27356	54948	19911
EP300-FBXW11-LRP6	51387	7749	39604	26908	55449	EP300-LRP6-WNT2	4956	43850	46302	4230	21219
EP300-GSK3B-RHOU	18018	15875	23808	17448	24731	DVLI-EP300-SFRP4	20719	16744	18619	55573	10227
AES-EP300-FBXW2	37663	38475	8684	26951	43448	EP300-WNT1-WNT2	1580	44154	51942	5979	10465
EP300-WNT1-WNT2B	2458	13992	29930	2629	26795	EP300-GSK3B-TCF7	10805	6455	14967	4039	31117
AXINI-DVLI-EP300	3584	5186	25284	4738	39794	AXINI-EP300-LRP5	46163	2225	27682	55146	32996
DKK1-EP300-FRZB	6801	5011	12885	30599	43081	EP300-GSK3B-SEN2	8327	37174	36829	10925	19701
FZD5-CCND1-EP300	2650	37698	56502	40799	52677	EP300-RHOU-WNT2	9914	43007	45594	678	52515
DVLI-EP300-TCF7	50918	34541	3163	55278	13295	AES-EP300-WNT5A	40140	51612	23938	4009	35408
EP300-FZD2-FZD7	16954	49764	37714	257	32349	AXINI-EP300-RHOU	31074	6355	22262	56648	46901
EP300-FOXN1-TLE2	1483	17209	53526	19752	11793	EP300-LRP6-TCF7	2128	9836	35075	32339	23660
EP300-WNT1-WNT3A	1327	24404	26980	31626	25194	EP300-FZD2-SFRP4	2005	26142	28568	1038	19151
EP300-LRP6-RHOU	2252	29244	36048	53718	12738	DVLI-EP300-SLC9A3R1	53857	20248	11438	50841	13844
AES-EP300-FOSL1	43507	49548	17732	5048	38399	EP300-FGF4-FRAT1	2201	12179	25784	4990	46565
EP300-FOXN1-SFRP4	1251	4474	55453	13622	8030	EP300-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2486	110	54841	38583	4454
AES-EP300-TCF7L1	40724	47358	6323	29692	43075	EP300-FZD2-SEN2	4197	39519	18150	40601	47963
EP300-FGF4-FOSL1	4014	52588	15864	2361	53651	EP300-WNT1-WNT5A	2374	24154	16830	20295	34795
AES-EP300-TLE2	39879	47530	4903	40946	36137	EP300-GSK3B-SFRP4	8611	32039	42196	33914	2265
EP300-FOXN1-FRAT1	1892	1651	56769	4475	20697	AXINI-EP300-SLC9A3R1	55614	15848	7372	37686	44246
EP300-GSK3B-WNT2B	17031	3072	9839	9763	7695	EP300-FGF4-WNT2	4612	34033	39415	40763	15139
AES-EP300-PITX2	46927	53837	1549	50756	32506	AXINI-EP300-FBXW4	39191	32647	632	24287	49848
EP300-LRP6-SLC9A3R1	14878	54303	41153	14723	43225	EP300-GSK3B-WNT2	39218	19231	50369	11449	1474
EP300-GSK3A-SEN2	699	37681	53286	49758	22127	DVLI-EP300-FBXW4	42764	5391	2864	37529	23352
EP300-FZD2-WNT2B	10327	30918	21265	5368	12988	EP300-FBXW11-WNT2	28485	14388	54560	3248	12860
EP300-GSK3A-WNT2	11607	41760	54123	6698	20631	AES-EP300-NLK	38886	52106	1233	23736	42435
AXINI-EP300-FRZB	24331	5929	26268	54326	22003	EP300-PORCN-SEN2	6992	46691	29845	18550	22225
EP300-JUN-TLE2	7910	43504	27573	32054	25082	EP300-FZD2-PPP2CA	8059	21295	864	5359	44323
AES-EP300-FZD8	42215	43804	6126	33921	25164	EP300-FOXN1-FZD7	3215	8590	56511	7008	39469
EP300-GSK3B-SLC9A3R1	36320	50164	49824	9817	11726	EP300-PYG01-WNT2	5709	43420	44821	441	34191
DVLI-EP300-FZD8	47942	8331	10133	56556	21119	DVLI-EP300-WNT5A	45556	27855	659	56344	29253
EP300-FZD2-LRP5	36812	15690	6117	6565	23126	EP300-PORCN-WNT4	5823	49192	43675	49247	45902
EP300-FOXN1-PPP2R1A	1354	35385	45759	2306	27930	AXINI-EP300-SEN2	19823	15581	10252	51019	28168
EP300-FOXN1-FZD1	800	1001	54131	249	2703	EP300-FOXN1-TCF7L1	1435	5591	57140	32094	6830
EP300-FZD2-WNT2	16652	30806	29163	34567	17667	EP300-JUN-WIF1	11523	21819	31185	9903	31253
AES-EP300-PPP2CA	40675	14926	3496	32198	22117	EP300-PORCN-SFRP1	25523	50771	36657	24398	41003
EP300-LRP6-FBXW4	2183	36856	32532	30812	36337	DKK1-EP300-LRP5	52435	1604	7145	16640	29132
EP300-SLC9A3R1-WNT2	12103	46092	24912	6681	4849	CCND1-CTBP1-EP300	31521	40575	10441	16973	2244
CTBP2-CTNNB1-EP300	30000	37842	42325	7348	17273	DVLI-EP300-KREMEN1	54034	12200	13668	57031	15029
EP300-PORCN-SFRP4	1223	52664	18944	37247	43717	DIXDC1-EP300-FBXW11	24668	2475	1975	54678	8438
EP300-FOXN1-FZD6	2964	2284	38649	17089	43579	EP300-FRZB-FZD1	35048	46610	23256	469	13611
EP300-FOXN1-LRP5	4494	2900	43340	32353	1904	AXINI-EP300-FZD1	31915	846	24550	32377	43633
EP300-PORCN-PPP2R1A	9705	56176	25373	738	50930	EP300-FZD2-WNT4	7958	30171	46102	282	28923
AXINI-EP300-WNT3A	29773	11569	2079	55580	29836	EP300-FZD2-TCF7L1	16132	9911	19549	19635	28746
AES-EP300-WNT2	41014	49014	5733	12100	31675	EP300-FZD2-PITX2	21066	1261	6278	52068	50788
DVLI-EP300-TCF7L1	52409	38334	12684	54201	14361	AES-EP300-KREMEN1	46085	42522	27876	8199	46619
EP300-FZD2-LEF1	22014	24731	6164	1694	20705	EP300-PORCN-WNT2B	15830	18382	7434	20043	39500
AXINI-EP300-LRP6	48971	2895	29183	50900	39151	DVLI-EP300-PITX2	56689	28520	27891	57038	12113
DKK1-EP300-SEN2	8223	22887	7362	18319	12719	EP300-GSK3A-NLK	1488	36811	54049	43805	46079
EP300-FBXW11-SEN2	28012	28278	53048	10057	32539	EP300-FOXN1-WNT2B	3438	4494	43475	1580	25168
EP300-FBXW11-FBXW4	40244	31834	28900	400	16176	EP300-FGF4-PPP2R1A	434	56284	13608	15792	27194
FZD5-CCND1-EP300	14768	7896	41900	37382	55614	EP300-JUN-PPP2R1A	5997	52619	15125	40032	31600
EP300-FOXN1-RHOU	1535	1411	47672	37234	19244	EP300-FOXN1-WNT4	1123	1458	56189	3851	27498
EP300-GSK3B-LRP5	26984	34947	6303	3091	5561	AXINI-EP300-WNT5A	45393	1954	35430	55047	50435
EP300-NKD1-WNT2	39516	745	54249	16318	30610	AXINI-EP300-WNT4	36955	1563	18777	20017	24055
EP300-GSK3B-FBXW4	22624	38473	17932	6602	3482	AXINI-EP300-PITX2	56749	23129	25963	57120	24869
EP300-FOXN1-GSK3B	2642	3165	56576	55942	32657	EP300-PORCN-TCF7L1	21837	509	26965	44207	37905
EP300-LRP6-SFRP4	2105	53738	39562	38275	32599	EP300-GSK3A-WNT2B	1984	14463	31882	45984	24146

Table 2: Rankings of EP300-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of WNT-EP300-X combinations

Sun et al. [16] report that the transcriptional coactivator p300 interacts with β -catenin in vitro and in vivo and is critical for β -catenin-mediated neoplastic transformation.

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_2	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_2	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
DVL1-EP300-LRP5	47629	11171	36648	32190	16061	AES-EP300-FRZB	31446	36375	44857	33083	1948
DVL1-EP300-FRZB	31326	2388	40229	31989	15925	AXIN1-EP300-GSK3B	51438	5515	51924	49857	2197
DVL1-EP300-GSK3B	55354	4660	50878	34110	17508	DVL1-EP300-WNT2B	44498	7790	46717	29455	10013
AES-EP300-TCF7	28477	15934	22392	27747	48675	AES-EP300-FZD1	28682	48775	38990	30063	4967
AES-EP300-SENP2	27514	29223	14109	27550	56692	DVL1-EP300-WNT4	6957	41307	26582	26171	51444
DVL1-EP300-FBXW11	37066	47790	44925	43438	13996	DVL1-EP300-FZD1	38055	4507	44330	42299	12832
AXIN1-EP300-TCF7	6026	48929	985	540	51171	EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	11605	22398	6349	16123	55238
EP300-FBXW11-LRP6	35868	49480	48658	46877	13344	EP300-LRP6-WNT2	29275	45803	45088	31443	130
EP300-GSK3B-RHOU	28851	26054	39632	40333	5598	DVL1-EP300-SFRP4	1671	17253	24724	26685	46394
AES-EP300-FBXW2	24400	10280	10114	26006	24431	EP300-WNT1-WNT2	32997	22960	44300	32979	4761
EP300-WNT1-WNT2B	24766	7961	7149	6651	57039	EP300-GSK3B-TCF7	19826	32409	7248	22915	48157
AXIN1-DVL1-EP300	41338	18502	44289	40531	36009	AXIN1-EP300-LRP5	40579	36695	42552	45104	8526
DKK1-EP300-FRZB	49700	19517	40133	36623	21443	EP300-GSK3B-SENP2	26252	6795	3095	116	51289
FZD5-CCND1-EP300	2726	18592	18103	13362	53081	EP300-RHOU-WNT2	37890	54029	40466	39394	16693
DVL1-EP300-TCF7	19324	56178	10115	21622	46042	AES-EP300-WNT5A	29197	43023	38116	41964	4843
EP300-FZD2-FZD7	25305	1054	6125	10063	46301	AXIN1-EP300-RHOU	50173	48448	31004	55578	3620
EP300-FOXN1-TLE2	25264	3588	9029	20821	56127	EP300-LRP6-TCF7	29571	28924	44410	29485	2498
EP300-WNT1-WNT3A	23045	8793	21877	20602	35795	EP300-FZD2-SFRP4	25848	4661	24079	13363	39344
EP300-LRP6-RHOU	25402	23591	17851	28391	33698	DVL1-EP300-SLC9A3R1	317	22223	15983	27172	30076
AES-EP300-FOSL1	27689	20431	21551	25851	56678	EP300-FGF4-FRAT1	28283	15095	9139	11230	48178
EP300-FOXN1-SFRP4	36662	55716	51828	41279	1706	EP300-FOXN1-KREMEN1	23162	5450	14335	12286	51032
AES-EP300-TCF7L1	28687	41224	34791	29425	8446	EP300-FZD2-SENP2	26521	5064	8139	1866	53435
EP300-FGF4-FOSL1	28028	36636	4319	2494	42274	EP300-WNT1-WNT5A	26125	33898	12493	14926	56427
AES-EP300-TLE2	29233	43682	39218	35095	2538	EP300-GSK3B-SFRP4	22272	21522	17742	27249	52827
EP300-FOXN1-FRAT1	33439	56590	46308	36232	22363	AXIN1-EP300-SLC9A3R1	5514	681	314	11396	30607
EP300-GSK3B-WNT2B	30525	47975	41708	29146	6959	EP300-FGF4-WNT2	26777	7434	18986	26489	48768
AES-EP300-PITX2	27429	13782	22774	24073	54041	AXIN1-EP300-FBXW4	30091	4658	56881	49861	16727
EP300-LRP6-SLC9A3R1	29346	29350	49014	29338	4481	EP300-GSK3B-WNT2	26634	9221	15474	28021	50171
EP300-GSK3A-SENP2	22650	3603	25430	2239	48957	DVL1-EP300-FBXW4	55496	40064	32475	30461	10767
EP300-FZD2-WNT2B	46392	56011	38190	42153	55470	EP300-FBXW11-WNT2	29136	33842	51961	42477	12798
EP300-GSK3A-WNT2	24886	5992	4517	118	52680	AES-EP300-NLK	28608	36332	44162	32492	15003
AXIN1-EP300-FRZB	55378	48682	51452	43815	26522	EP300-PORCN-SENP2	36219	52222	49967	38629	2872
EP300-JUN-TLE2	15132	4321	12651	12567	50557	EP300-FZD2-PPP2CA	26266	2702	16127	4968	42671
AES-EP300-FZD8	30473	35793	38115	30018	3470	EP300-FOXN1-FZD7	34199	56307	47659	35246	3318
EP300-GSK3B-SLC9A3R1	23667	1057	5603	5649	55505	EP300-PYGO1-WNT2	31940	56694	45844	45742	12882
DVL1-EP300-FZD8	37705	27056	47763	29791	8005	DVL1-EP300-WNT5A	50248	16218	30548	30959	5678
EP300-FZD2-LRP5	28767	53203	42333	55461	2149	EP300-PORCN-WNT4	30024	54987	52222	44421	1005
EP300-FOXN1-PPP2R1A	27453	4062	5453	17377	46862	AXIN1-EP300-SENP2	6693	13227	2179	6278	13995
EP300-FOXN1-FZD1	24650	2174	7020	18549	42933	EP300-FOXN1-TCF7L1	18382	51779	7011	7436	53365
EP300-FZD2-WNT2	10749	1114	18935	14993	1647	EP300-JUN-WIF1	42039	52746	44541	44510	6591
AES-EP300-PPP2CA	27875	26880	13013	26533	45960	EP300-PORCN-SFRP1	17781	3342	8566	8584	55892
EP300-LRP6-FBXW4	27805	27687	8142	27821	52868	DKK1-EP300-LRP5	30895	31043	39171	36014	17746
EP300-SLC9A3R1-WNT2	20616	11781	23387	9871	38341	CCND1-CTBP1-EP300	52957	53613	52910	56812	8011
CTBP2-CTNNB1-EP300	8572	27644	14585	18504	31799	DVL1-EP300-KREMEN1	53244	4343	43692	35471	20160
EP300-PORCN-SFRP4	39355	53777	48569	48546	1266	DIXDC1-EP300-FBXW11	16478	41314	19565	26955	35640
EP300-FOXN1-FZD6	23019	824	9456	21888	53832	EP300-FRZB-FZD1	32433	42763	45343	48398	29652
EP300-FOXN1-LRP5	15128	10594	24621	20523	53107	AXIN1-EP300-FZD1	30516	41369	54535	55967	10843
EP300-PORCN-PPP2R1A	22470	6955	21990	5623	28699	EP300-FZD2-WNT4	19650	3017	21932	18595	4530
AXIN1-EP300-WNT3A	44869	1061	56466	48992	26794	EP300-FZD2-TCF7L1	43797	55416	38777	36725	56055
AES-EP300-WNT2	27810	23094	21088	25883	54150	EP300-FZD2-PITX2	24012	15242	9973	25729	44122
DVL1-EP300-TCF7L1	37881	971	47084	35493	11145	AES-EP300-KREMEN1	29288	36103	39298	31122	2254
EP300-FZD2-LEF1	28380	3995	14801	1687	55022	EP300-PORCN-WNT2B	15324	657	8664	22349	56194
AXIN1-EP300-LRP6	2947	29232	6821	5511	49217	DVL1-EP300-PITX2	548	36053	11918	25848	49131
DKK1-EP300-SENP2	637	29230	15980	14884	49492	EP300-GSK3A-NLK	29885	38529	45890	51667	3052
EP300-FBXW11-SENP2	30483	18432	36975	37782	3025	EP300-FOXN1-WNT2B	26241	26000	16286	1066	36461
EP300-FBXW11-FBXW4	26223	12173	5178	3696	41445	EP300-FGF4-PPP2R1A	28963	23170	45747	34094	8154
FZD5-CCND1-EP300	32144	42830	41267	51303	51382	EP300-JUN-PPP2R1A	7366	1840	9839	10599	24170
EP300-FOXN1-RHOU	26248	42738	21869	28309	36706	EP300-FOXN1-WNT4	41075	30320	34858	36415	636
EP300-GSK3B-LRP5	36514	45021	38411	51259	4464	AXIN1-EP300-WNT5A	47677	47620	52664	49981	17016
EP300-NKD1-WNT2	20461	1679	17555	936	16564	AXIN1-EP300-WNT4	9475	9841	4537	7168	40103
EP300-GSK3B-FBXW4	34810	35670	39409	29935	4265	AXIN1-EP300-PITX2	1837	53367	4684	5496	23397
EP300-FOXN1-GSK3B	24125	55928	7755	17549	51696	EP300-PORCN-TCF7L1	19874	8888	6449	9131	43057
EP300-LRP6-SFRP4	30263	17567	42981	29005	4067	EP300-GSK3A-WNT2B	32216	51042	52624	57038	4412

Table 3: Rankings of EP300-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

Also, it is known that the concentration of β -catenin is regulated by the WNT signaling. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of WNT family along with EP300, to be prominent at 3rd order level - EP300-WNT1-

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_2	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_2	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
DVL1-EP300-LRP5	16128	2668	3508	25585	49564	AES-EP300-FRZB	22478	19042	39478	49345	10677
DVL1-EP300-FRZB	45916	23295	41040	25372	21806	AXIN1-EP300-GSK3B	25017	31769	45778	24411	46341
DVL1-EP300-GSK3B	19402	18834	13941	37122	53746	DVL1-EP300-WNT2B	8726	18065	22256	42886	36883
AES-EP300-TCF7	3396	6786	37096	29068	55834	AES-EP300-FZD1	13120	51618	37147	48788	11330
AES-EP300-SEN2	3503	32175	28924	49375	20292	DVL1-EP300-WNT4	25389	12501	1599	51389	44362
DVL1-EP300-FBXW11	48172	9942	45046	33611	19779	DVL1-EP300-FZD1	45075	22334	47343	29898	28970
AXIN1-EP300-TCF7	48798	45691	6057	26762	42276	EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	32750	6325	30769	2643	11537
EP300-FBXW11-LRP6	42949	589	50439	52548	56135	EP300-LRP6-WNT2	29679	33659	13515	21138	29749
EP300-GSK3B-RHOU	12504	36745	3027	13814	10645	DVL1-EP300-SFRP4	19925	13204	4321	52486	37382
AES-EP300-FBXW2	16985	4300	18647	16841	43938	EP300-WNT1-WNT2	46394	8408	1307	35073	31460
EP300-WNT1-WNT2B	40403	45788	6306	37531	53145	EP300-GSK3B-TCF7	19181	34625	21224	7831	12752
AXIN1-DVL1-EP300	41294	32137	43923	557	23972	AXIN1-EP300-LRP5	11247	55837	44467	27212	38032
DKK1-EP300-FRZB	7126	791	28396	14813	54053	EP300-GSK3B-SEN2	20604	44330	12414	20857	50439
FZD5-CCND2-EP300	49587	56726	22257	10438	37842	EP300-RHOU-WNT2	48627	4883	16855	50530	27850
DVL1-EP300-TCF7	9873	6624	2766	52866	2867	AES-EP300-WNT5A	29498	5467	36624	45146	8858
EP300-FZD2-FZD7	10225	24068	57070	35242	7515	AXIN1-EP300-RHOU	16298	47098	45733	28449	24757
EP300-FOXN1-TLE2	18282	45030	23829	56381	38000	EP300-LRP6-TCF7	40090	22622	38531	46131	49889
EP300-WNT1-WNT3A	35049	51879	24918	13081	9432	EP300-FZD2-SFRP4	16970	28429	56137	32136	8095
EP300-LRP6-RHOU	9608	33908	56852	12352	18335	DVL1-EP300-SLC9A3R1	2474	8012	3321	54284	9451
AES-EP300-FOSL1	2076	9358	40678	41334	55550	EP300-FGF4-FRAT1	36332	37765	20615	3058	7021
EP300-FOXN1-SFRP4	40810	28753	11476	55850	28406	EP300-FOXN1-KREMEN1	23284	7607	24950	49468	6281
AES-EP300-TCF7L1	16775	37790	29208	41754	7930	EP300-FZD2-SEN2	35835	24234	56494	55323	8173
EP300-FGF4-FOSL1	33196	23070	26711	8374	5298	EP300-WNT1-WNT5A	18070	53885	18563	56960	314
AES-EP300-TLE2	21327	28702	29958	43439	13253	EP300-GSK3B-SFRP4	31455	30086	20775	3184	52407
EP300-FOXN1-FRAT1	43464	28924	224	55362	45013	AXIN1-EP300-SLC9A3R1	49588	52265	9990	25548	1811
EP300-GSK3B-WNT2B	39896	34405	6246	29749	20434	EP300-FGF4-WNT2	8316	6747	54293	54505	24752
AES-EP300-PITX2	1201	15547	40455	15398	55710	AXIN1-EP300-FBXW4	7344	40069	39336	36579	34280
EP300-LRP6-SLC9A3R1	20200	30562	34241	44811	7902	EP300-GSK3B-WNT2	10826	3296	50380	11425	37468
EP300-GSK3A-SEN2	21983	22548	37488	6292	39982	DVL1-EP300-FBXW4	26785	39780	62	43757	32072
EP300-FZD2-WNT2B	52134	32789	7430	43890	27221	EP300-FBXW11-WNT2	30888	13840	12313	7488	37696
EP300-GSK3A-WNT2	20603	33930	24951	10990	49921	AES-EP300-NLK	10828	53497	40369	49022	8923
AXIN1-EP300-FRZB	30988	52709	46207	1111	56125	EP300-PORCN-SEN2	53629	5779	12021	9758	27766
EP300-JUN-TLE2	42697	22782	17194	5473	37014	EP300-FZD2-PPP2CA	8595	21744	56912	41698	6259
AES-EP300-FZD8	21822	28045	33872	44482	11059	EP300-FOXN1-FZD7	50072	34686	26942	55845	26471
EP300-GSK3B-SLC9A3R1	11822	49282	8181	4251	31233	EP300-PYG01-WNT2	48602	27784	3033	4313	26421
DVL1-EP300-FZD8	5476	12856	40077	40351	35656	DVL1-EP300-WNT5A	18933	25983	3336	33670	35252
EP300-FZD2-LRP5	15328	37463	51195	41264	20668	EP300-PORCN-WNT4	22842	5697	24417	11816	30962
EP300-FOXN1-PPP2R1A	2782	54679	56277	56440	4527	AXIN1-EP300-SEN2	53739	32169	5543	41242	12080
EP300-FOXN1-FZD1	3620	44573	56341	55752	54953	EP300-FOXN1-TCF7L1	11326	48294	56344	56291	27463
EP300-FZD2-WNT2	37269	43731	22218	13348	5654	EP300-JUN-WIF1	41696	318	254	3586	37500
AES-EP300-PPP2CA	2675	16717	54436	50242	55608	EP300-PORCN-SFRP1	33178	57058	22324	8111	35864
EP300-LRP6-FBXW4	18808	18777	56049	20821	55972	DKK1-EP300-LRP5	5634	29755	30411	21952	39125
EP300-SLC9A3R1-WNT2	2738	53585	42698	23445	7600	CCND1-CTBP1-EP300	43260	44313	33427	20284	31987
CTBP2-CTNNB1-EP300	54101	30198	36185	5573	44643	DVL1-EP300-KREMEN1	10232	7708	9155	50244	56618
EP300-PORCN-SFRP4	52408	48976	4006	14306	37062	DIXDC1-EP300-FBXW11	22658	1104	15939	45977	30698
EP300-FOXN1-FZD6	27543	45980	55954	56348	57	EP300-FRZB-FZD1	40071	17497	38953	22178	19865
EP300-FOXN1-LRP5	22535	19228	52434	55247	5512	AXIN1-EP300-FZD1	6966	43637	46156	43046	39527
EP300-PORCN-PPP2R1A	27723	53765	27214	12840	4389	EP300-FZD2-WNT4	33751	52611	43967	7129	6623
AXIN1-EP300-WNT3A	14085	34473	45814	16882	56289	EP300-FZD2-TCF7L1	53434	39391	6990	45299	20020
AES-EP300-WNT2	3457	10676	41634	9595	55060	EP300-FZD2-PITX2	42426	55258	55923	31463	6536
DVL1-EP300-TCF7L1	7070	30158	17550	39128	56391	AES-EP300-KREMEN1	20293	34511	35279	44682	8912
EP300-FZD2-LEF1	3926	55500	56113	47260	11933	EP300-PORCN-WNT2B	34780	53516	18975	9236	50588
AXIN1-EP300-LRP6	47049	53778	21266	21014	8160	DVL1-EP300-PITX2	3179	18813	1618	47057	47210
DKK1-EP300-SEN2	2498	31495	2284	24514	22652	EP300-GSK3A-NLK	29218	53879	34237	18183	8594
EP300-FBXW11-SEN2	31107	47738	2076	29965	26445	EP300-FOXN1-WNT2B	20661	55248	37791	3285	7232
EP300-FBXW11-FBXW4	34643	51680	21827	17505	13661	EP300-FGF4-PPP2R1A	27200	21724	3067	2038	49507
FZD5-CCND1-EP300	9586	52993	9363	38036	23801	EP300-JUN-PPP2R1A	31760	54584	34286	9593	22982
EP300-FOXN1-RHOU	205	16819	22913	48335	47122	EP300-FOXN1-WNT4	50388	45705	37311	35769	16189
EP300-GSK3B-LRP5	31751	39425	11199	23677	13632	AXIN1-EP300-WNT5A	14220	28915	40087	2321	27392
EP300-NKD1-WNT2	29946	36083	40149	5901	8420	AXIN1-EP300-WNT4	47589	37668	12889	10232	9407
EP300-GSK3B-FBXW4	40081	19530	25809	1044	13672	AXIN1-EP300-PITX2	35819	48198	7128	5864	15595
EP300-FOXN1-GSK3B	14972	44715	43280	56927	7539	EP300-PORCN-TCF7L1	29464	15052	15216	9453	48089
EP300-LRP6-SFRP4	46454	27378	4066	47717	37002	EP300-GSK3A-WNT2B	38348	734	10336	33909	12142

Table 4: Rankings of EP300-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

WNT2B, EP300-WNT1-WNT3A, EP300-GSK3B-WNT2B, EP300-FZD2-WNT2B, EP300-GSK3A-WNT2, EP300-FZD2-WNT2, EP300-SLC9A3R1-WNT2, AXIN1-EP300-WNT3A, AES-EP300-WNT2, EP300-NKD1-WNT2, DVL1-EP300-WNT2B, DVL1-EP300-WNT4,

EP300-LRP6-WNT2, EP300-WNT1-WNT2, EP300-RHOU-WNT2, AES-EP300-WNT5A, EP300-WNT1-WNT5A, EP300-FGF4-WNT2, EP300-GSK3B-WNT2, EP300-FBXW11-WNT2, EP300-PYGO1-WNT2, DVL1-EP300-WNT5A, EP300-PORCN-WNT4, EP300-FZD2-WNT4, EP300-PORCN-WNT2B, EP300-FOXN1-WNT2B, EP300-FOXN1-WNT4, AXIN1-EP300-WNT5A, AXIN1-EP300-WNT4 and EP300-GSK3A-WNT2B. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.5. Examining the behaviour of FZD-EP300-X combinations

It is known that WNT signaling involves the binding of a WNT-protein ligand to a Frizzled (FZD) family receptor, which passes the biological signal to the Dishevelled (DVL) protein inside the cell. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of FZD family along with EP300, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FZD5-CCND2-EP300, EP300-FZD2-FZD7, EP300-FZD2-WNT2B, AES-EP300-FZD8, DVL1-EP300-FZD8, EP300-FZD2-LRP5, EP300-FOXN1-FZD1, EP300-FZD2-WNT2, EP300-FOXN1-FZD6, EP300-FZD2-LEF1, FZD5-CCND1-EP300, AES-EP300-FZD1, DVL1-EP300-FZD1, EP300-FZD2-SFRP4, EP300-FZD2-SEN2, EP300-FZD2-PPP2CA, EP300-FOXN1-FZD7, EP300-FRZB-FZD1, AXIN1-EP300-FZD1, EP300-FZD2-WNT4, EP300-FZD2-TCF7L1 and EP300-FZD2-PITX2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.6. Examining the behaviour of SENP2-EP300-X combinations

Yang et al. [19] identified PRICKLE3, TNFSF10, ACSL1 and EP300 as potential key gene regulators associated with primary resistance, and SNW1, SENP2 and SMNDC1 as key gene regulators associated with acquired resistance. These findings offered valuable insights for understanding chemotherapy resistance and related gene signatures in small-cell lung cancer (SCLC), which could help further biological validation studies. It is not known whether EP300 and SENP2 work synergistically, but looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for SENP2 along with EP300, to be prominent at 3rd order level - AES-EP300-SENP2, EP300-GSK3A-SENP2, DKK1-EP300-SENP2, EP300-FBXW11-SENP2, EP300-GSK3B-SENP2, EP300-FZD2-SENP2, EP300-PORCN-SENP2 and AXIN1-EP300-SENP2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.7. Examining the behaviour of JUN-EP300-X combinations

Kawasaki et al. [20] suggest that activation transcription factor-2 (ATF2) and p300 cooperate in the control of transcription by forming a protein complex that is responsive to differentiation-inducing signals, such as RA or E1A, and the phosphorylation of ATF2 by protein kinase C alpha (PKC alpha) is probably a signaling event in the pathway that leads to the transactivation of the c-JUN gene in F9 cells. Further, Maggirwar et al. [21] observed that expression of RELA (NF- κ B) suppressed the c-JUN-dependent

transcription of c-JUN, and this effect was reversed by overexpression of p300. RELA's effects on c-JUN transcription were mediated by competitive binding of the carboxy-terminal region of RELA to the CH1 domain of p300, which also binds to c-JUN; deletion of this region abrogated the ability of RELA to inhibit c-JUN activity. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for JUN along with EP300, to be prominent at 3rd order level - EP300-JUN-TLE2, EP300-JUN-KREMEN1, EP300-JUN-WIF1 and EP300-JUN-PPP2R1A. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of EP300 in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the EP300, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

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Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For EP300, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for

3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

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